

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Usar 1, a salinity- and alkalinity-tolerant rice for Uttar Pradesh

D. M. Maurya, H. G. Singh, and K. N. Dwivedi, C. S. Azad University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

Usar 1, a medium-maturing salinity- and alkalinity-tolerant rice variety, was released in May 1984 for cultivation in Uttar Pradesh. It was developed in Kanpur from Jaya/Getu and tested in the All India Coordinated Saline-Alkaline Resistance Varietal Trials in 1980-82 (Table 1) and in station trials from 1978 to 1983 (Table 2). Usar 1 is semitall, tillers moderately, matures in 128-135 d, and has high yield potential. Grains are short and bold with

good cooking quality. It is resistant to bacterial leaf blight and bacterial leaf streak, and moderately resistant to major

insect pests. Usar 1 is a good substitute for Jaya and traditional varieties in alkaline areas. □

Table 2. Performance of Usar 1 in state and coordinated varietal trials. UP, India.

Year and location	Yield (t/ha)		CD at 5%	Days to maturity		pH
	Usar 1	Jaya		Usar 1	Jaya	
Daleep Nagar, Kanpur						
1978	2.9	1.7	0.5	132	134	9.3
1979	3.7	2.1	0.6	133	134	9.5
1980	1.5	0.6	0.8	135	136	9.2
1981	5.3	4.6	1.1	132	135	9.1
1982	4.0	3.5	0.7	134	134	9.6
1983	4.2	3.5	0.8			
Kumarganj, Faizabad						
1978	3.0	2.0	0.4	128	132	9.1
1980	4.0	2.8	0.6	132	135	9.5
1981	4.0	3.5	0.5	134	136	9.5
1982	3.8	3.3	0.9	140	145	9.5

Table 1. Grain yield and ancillary characters of Usar 1 and Jaya at various locations, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Trial, 1982 kharif. ^a UP, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)							Days to 50% flowering	Panicles/m ²
	Alkaline locations			Saline locations					
	Raipuram	CSSRI Karnal	Kumarganj Faizabad	Pondicherry	Panvel Raigarh	Keshpur	Vytilla		
Usar 1	1.7	3.4	3.8	0.9	2.4	1.1	9.5	101	348
Jaya	1.5	2.2	3.3	1.94	2.6	0.3	6.6	106	249
CD at 5%	ns	1.3	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.4	ns		
pH	9.5	9.1-9.8	9.6	na	7.5	6.0	na		
Ec	3.5	na	1.2	na	2.5-5.2	3.5-5.0	na		

^a ns = nonsignificant, na = not available.

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HIGH TEMPERATURE

Tolerance of two rice lines for high temperature at meiosis and anthesis

D. R. Khan, research scholar, and D. J. Mackill, associate plant breeder, IIRRI

Growth chamber and field experiments have shown that rice plants are susceptible to high temperatures at reproductive stage. Studies at IIRRI have shown that rice plants are most sensitive to high tempera-

ture during anthesis, and are slightly less sensitive about 10 d before flowering (booting or meiotic stage). Several varieties with tolerance for high temperature during anthesis have been identified. The most common tolerance mechanism appears to be the ability to maintain high anther dehiscence and pollen shedding at high temperatures. The relation between tolerance at anthesis and tolerance at meiotic stage has not been determined. We

compared tolerance at those growth stages.

Four rice varieties were planted in 3.8-litre pots in the IIRRI phytotron on 2 dates in 2 replications. Treatments were control (29°C day/21°C night), 35°C/27°C for 5 d during flowering, and 35°C/27°C for 5 d beginning about 12 d before flowering. Each pot had 20 plants, tillers of which were trimmed to leave 1 main culm per plant. Flowering dates of each panicle were recorded.